

THE VĀSTUŚĀSTRAS OF WESTERN INDIA

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The early 11th century saw the culmination of the general Nāgara form of northern Indian temple architecture with its various ramifications in eastern and central India, and in Rajasthan and Gujarat in the western part of the sub-continent. The *vāstu* codes attributed to the schools of Garga¹, Kaśyapa², Parāśara³, Manu⁴, Mārkaṇḍeya⁵ and other ancient preceptors became, at this stage, outmoded: their terminology, by and large, grew obsolete; their vocabulary proved inadequate, archaic, and insufficient to portray the manifold architectural elaborations and decorative embellishments of the far evolved buildings now erected in an unprecedented number in these territories. This eventful and active epoch witnessed the ascendancy of four dynasties in central India after the break up of the Pratihāra empire. The Kalacūrī-Cedīs or Haihayas in Dāhala country, the Candellas in Jejakabhukti, the Kacchapaghātas in Gopagiri area, and the Paramāras in Mālava by now grew powerful as also tended to be mutually hostile. Though engaged in interwars, at times prolonged and protracted they never found the conditions that would substantially discourage in patronizing architectural activities. In point of fact, each kingdom vied with its neighbour in erecting ornate edifices for the brahmanical divinities in a spirit that was as much religious as it sometimes was militant in motive and ruthless in determination. The pontiffs of the Śaivaite Mattamayūra sect as also the Jainas of the Acela-Kṣapaṇaka sect, no less ambivalent, devotional, and missionary more than temporal in aims and ambitions, contributed a substantial share to the architectural undertakings in these provinces. In Rajasthan, the Cāhamānas of Śākambhari and of Naḍḍula, the Guhilas of Medapāta and the abbots of the Pāsupata Śaiva sect evinced strong passion for temple building during the tenth century. But the Cāhamānas, together with the Paramāras of Bhillamāla, Jābālipura, and of Candrāvati and Vatapura were eventually forced on the defensive against the growing prowess of the Solankīs of Gujarat who were emerging fast to the forefront and who, together with their Śvetāmbara Jaina ministers and merchant princes of the State, were to be hailed as the greatest patrons of architecture known to the mediaeval northern India. The catholicity of outlook of the Solankī monarchs and the opulence of their vast kingdom stood behind their great architectural projects - theistic, civic, and military - as endorsed by the countless ruined buildings of that age.

Śaivism, more than Bhāgavatism (Vaiṣṇavism), was at its climax in the medieval era; and Jainism never attained such heights before or after, particularly

in central and western India. Both faiths lost no time in giving material expression to their spiritual essence in the shape of temples they built. And they built with a premonition as though such good times shall never return. This was then an auspicious hour also for codifying the structural rules of architecture consolidated through intensive and unbroken building activity. The written rules, it possibly was hoped, may act as a regulator for the building processes and thus a useful guide to posterity; it could help keep the lamp of tradition burning, indeed with brilliance and assured continuance. Unfortunately, the medieval northern tradition of architecture could not survive except in Kalinga in the east and Rajasthan and Gujarat in the west, this largely was due to vicissitudes of various kinds, political disasters in particular which by and large resulted in the disappearance of patronage. With the extinction of the tradition of sacred architecture in these regions, a second misfortune that concomitantly came down was the loss of the *vāstuśāstras* pertaining to several of these medieval schools. The *vāstu* books relating to the splendid Khajurāho temples are so far unheard of. Those on Dāhala and Gopātri temples are yet to be discovered. For the Mālava territory, however, at least three works of considerable significance are now known, thanks to the preservation of their manuscripts in the Western Indian Jaina libraries and in the institutional and private collections, particularly those of the Śilpīs of Gujarat and Rajasthan. The *Jayaprcchā*, probably, the oldest of the trio, is unfortunately available only in fragments.⁶ The work, as an explicit statement in the *Aparājita-prcchā* purports to indicate, dealt with domestic, civic, and military architecture.⁷ The available portions of the *Jayaprcchā* endorse this statement. The work next in date, unhesitatingly the most important *vāstuśāstra* ever written in northern India, is the *Samarāṅgaṇasūtradhāra* (SS) of Bhojadeva of Dhārā. Bhoja himself, albeit, could not have written it. It is foregone that some learned architect composed it and ascribed it to his master's name. The composition could have taken place sometime between A. D. 1035 - the date of the foundation called "Sarasvatī-sadana" by Bhoja at Dhārā - and the latter's passing away in 1055. The text of SS has been in recent years subjected to studies.⁸ It is, therefore, unessential to enlarge upon its details at this place. The third work is a booklet entitled the *Pramāṇamañjarī* by Sūtradhāra Malla, son of Śilpī Nakula, who flourished during the régime of the Paramāra potentate Udayāditya in late 11th century. The text comprises some 304 verses and, according to the author, it is in part the précis of a particular portion of the *Jayaprcchā* (and some similar work in a form of dialogue between Jaya and Vikṣa) that dealt with the wooden architecture connected with domestic dwellings. The largest number of *vāstu* works, however, are available from Gujarat and Rajasthan. The liberal and unbroken temple-building activities by the Jainas in these two provinces has been instrumental in the survival, decadent though, of the western Indian or Maru-Gurjara tradition. And this continuity has been admittedly aided by the *vāstuśāstras* composed in the "High medieval"

times with which Śilpī had not lost touch so completely. Several of these works are still unpublished but otherwise accessible in manuscript form in the collections of various institutions, and Sompura Śilpī.⁹ At least four works attributable to the Solāṅkī period are known from Gujarat.

High Medieval

1. The *Vāstusāstra* of Viśvakarmā

This is the oldest available work on the Maru-Gurjara style of architecture which prevailed in Gujarat and southern and western Rajasthan from 11th century onwards. It has been noticed by T. Aufrescht in the *Catalogues Catalogorum*. The extracts and selected chapters from this work are found in a later compilation, *Śrījñānaratnakośa*. These afford some insight into the nature of its contents. A fairly large portion of the famous western Indian work, the *Aparājitapṛcchā*, particularly the one that deals with religious architecture, seems to have been based on this work.¹⁰ The text is in a form of a dialogue between Viśvakarmā and his first 'mind-born' son Jaya in emulation perhaps of the *Jayapṛcchā* and the *Samarāṅgaṇasūtradhāra*. The complete original work could have been fairly exhaustive in its treatment on almost all the aspects of temple architecture. And even as it is known in a truncated form, it still covers the most useful aspects, the total elevational details of the *prāsāda* and the *mandapa*. It is, moreover, replete with considerable originality; its injunctions, stated in the simplest Sanskrit, seem to be one of an assured authority. It ably reflects the particular stage of architectural development prevalent at the time of its composition. And this seems not later than the second half of the 11th century. This may be ascertained by the correspondence of mensural specifications and the associated detailed injunctions with the existing temples of that period in Gujarat. To quote only two instances, the formal specifications for the *pītha* and the *saṁvaranā vidhi* (construction of a belled stepped roof for the halls) prescribed in the text are, in their detailed aspects, applicable to the temples erected during the second quarter of 11th century.

2. The *Vāstuvīdyā* of Viśvakarmā

The work next in date appears to be this one. The complete manuscript of the work is still unknown. Stray chapters of the text nonetheless have been preserved in various collections.¹¹ The work goes by the title *Sūtrasantāna* in some of the manuscripts in addition to the usual appellation *Vāstuvīdyā*. A portion of the text is also traceable from later compilations ascribed to Jaya where it is referred to as *Jayamata*, *Jayoktavidhāna*, or *Jayasamhita*. Fortunately, the *Vāstuvīdyā* has been copiously used (both quoted and unquoted) in *Śrījñānaratnakośa*. All this material put together gives a consistent and fairly full knowledge on the metrography and elevational details of the temple in its entirety. The text is in a dialogue form between Viśvakarmā and Jaya imitating possibly the aforementioned *Vāstusāstra*. Like the *Vāstusāstra*, this too

was an extensive work on the Maru-Gurjara style. It, however, embodies a tradition that is different in its mensural aspects, and, to a small extent in the nomenclature and in a few details, from the former text though perfectly within the ambit of the western Indian style of architecture. It represents a slightly different tradition and recollects the experiences of a different guild. And it seems to have been composed at a date slightly later than the *Vāstuśāstra*. All the same, the influence of the latter work on the *Vāstuvidyā* is very slight in phraseology and format and is suspected only in a few subjects such as the *pītha* (*socle*) and the *dhvajadaṇḍa* (flag-staff).¹² The individualism of the *Vāstuvidyā* in regard to diction and content is demonstrably in evidence.¹³ Since Jaya appears as a character in both the works, the chances of confusing them were many. And for us the difficulties are aggravated when passages from both the works are incorporated in compilations without specifically referring to either. However, the main sources for the restoration (or rather re-assembling) of both these works are such compilations and omnibus manuscripts. The guiding factor in such cases is the style of expression which differs in mannerism and preferences in the two works under reference. The *Vāstuśāstra* uses a more precise, simpler, but a masculine style of writing. The *Vāstuvidyā* leans towards elegance, lyricism, wordiness, and expansivity. It luxuriates in a nasal style, frequently ending in *anusvāra* in the opening verses of a chapter. In a reply to a question framed by Jaya, Viśvakarmā often starts with '*sādhu sādhu vatsa...*' an address not found in the *Vāstuśāstra*. The *Vāstuvidyā* did know the existence of the *Vāstuśāstra* but has largely preferred to remain independent of it in its treatment as well as exposition.

The *Vāstuvidyā* furnished very useful information on the *vāstu* rites, the installation ceremonies, the temple architecture, and iconography. Among the chapters on rites, those on *āya*, *vāstusalyoddhāra vidhi*, and the *maṇḍala-kunḍalā-vidhi* may be mentioned. As for temples, it deals with the structural rules and the general as well as special features of the *jagatī* (terrace), *pītha* (base), *kaṭi* (wall-face)¹⁴, the *śikhara* (spire), the *kapilā* (connecting vestibule), the 33 types of Prāgrīvādi *maṇḍapas*, the *karotaka* (large, central, domical ceiling), the *dhvajadaṇḍa*, the *garbhagrha* (cella), the *dvāraśākhā* (doorframe) and the locii of the eye-levels of gods. It also deals with the specific species of temples such as the 25 types of Kesarī series, the 21 types of Meru series, the 25 types of Sāgaratilakādi *prāsādas*, and the 52 types of the Jaina temples. Lucid and detailed descriptions of *Kirtistambhas* (pillars of fame), *pratolīs* (gateways), and *maṭhas* and *vihāras* (monasteries) also find place in the *Vāstuvidyā*. In iconography it treats the *liṅga* types, the 12 forms of Āditya, the nine Grahas or planets, the ten Dikpālas (Regents of the Quarters), the Saptā-Mātrkās (seven mother goddesses), the 24 forms of Pārvaṭī, the 12 forms of Sarasvatī, the *saṅghāta-mūrtis* (composite images) of Śiva with other gods, and finally the Vṛṣabha and the Garuḍa. What is more, it also furnishes a very valuable section on Jaina

iconography.¹⁵ The iconometry, too, of Brahmanical and Jaina deities has been well discussed in the VV. The later works, the *Dīpārnava* and the *Devatāmūrtiprakaraṇa*, particularly the former one, drew copiously from the *Vāstuvidyā*. By the analysis of its contents, the *Vāstuvidyā* seems to have been formulated in about the first half of 12th century, perhaps in lower southern Rajasthan. (The formal details of the *saṁvaraṇā* of its visualization are known from early 12th century. And its mention of the figure of Kāmadeva in the assembly of the bracket-figures for the *karotaka*-ceiling indicates lower Rajasthan as its provenance.)

3. The *Aparājītapṛcchā*

One of the most authentic works and the one which exercised considerable influence on a number of later works on *vāstu*, is this comprehensive compendium cast in a dialogue form between Viśvakarmā and his fourth 'mind-born' son, Aparājīta. The date of its composition seems, on the strength of a vast body of internal evidence, late 12th or early 13th century and probably the period of the Solāṅkī monarch Bhīmadeva II (1177-1240).¹⁷ It covers a wider canvas in the selection of topics on architecture though not always exhaustive in its treatment. Besides the *Vāstusāstra* on which perhaps it depends heavily as alluded to previously, it has been appreciably influenced by the *Samarāṅgaṇasūtradhāra*.¹⁸ Possibly it also knew the *Vāstuvidyā*¹⁹ though seems to rely more on the *Vāstusāstra* for treating the same subject. To some extent the *Jayapṛcchā* could be the source of extraction for the civic and domestic architecture in AP. And for the subject of *rekhā* or curvature of the *sikhara*, it also used the *Rekhārnava* (c. late 10th or early 11th century), a brief text that may have been composed in the Mālava country. Since the AP text is available in printed form, it will be superfluous to go into all its details save noticing its salient features. Besides devoting several chapters on the *vāstu* rites, astronomical-astrological aspects, domestic, imperial, civic, and military architecture, it dwells on the origin of temples, their 14 classes and other sub-species, also the elevational aspects of the temples, various categories of the *mandapas*, the *vitānas* (ceilings), the *saṁvaraṇā*, the *rekhās*, the doorframes, the *torānas* and the monasteries. It also provides for a large section on iconography, treating as it does the details of a variety of *liṅgas*, Ekādaśa Rudras, various forms of Viṣṇu as well as of Pārvaṭī, the Dikpālas, the attendants/door-guardians of different gods, and finally the Jaina Tirthankaras and their Yakṣas and Yakṣīs. The original contribution of the *Aparājītapṛcchā* as distinct from the *Samarāṅgaṇasūtradhāra*, the *Vāstusāstra* and the *Vāstuvidyā* is difficult to assess fully in the present state of our knowledge. What appears to be independent in AP may, in reality, be summaries it drew from sources not known today. The approach and methodology of the author of AP are of course his own, logical and distinctly individual. From the internal evidence, the work seems to have been composed late in the period of the Solāṅkī emperor Kumārapāla or Bhīmadeva II, and thus not later than the last quarter

of the 12th century.

4-5. The *Aparājītaprabhā* and the *Aparājītasamhitā*

The existence of these two works is known, but the details as to their contents are yet to come to light. The *Aparājītasamhitā* has been quoted in *Śrījñānaratnakośa* in the context of the locii of the eye-levels of the images of gods in the cella in relation to the door aperture. The description of *kirtistambha* found in one omnibus manuscript ascribes it to *Aparājīta*. It is not traceable in the *Aparājītaprcchā*. Perhaps it could be in the *Aparājītaprabhā*.²⁰

6. The *Jñānasāra-Aparājīta*

While Jaya was popular with the writers of the 11th century, *Aparājīta* figures as a favourite character with the *Vāstusāstra-kāras* of the later part of the 12th and the subsequent century. In JA he emerges now from the status of a recipient to that of an exalted one of a preceptor where he is portrayed as answering questions framed by Ācārya Vikṣa or Vaikṣa. Sixteen chapters covering about 405 verses are known from its available manuscript in the collection of late Shri Prabhashankarbhai. These pertain to *vāstu* rites, domestic architecture, and construction of water tanks. In age it seems for certain to be younger than the *Aparājītaprcchā*.

7. The *Viveka-vilāsa*

This is, like the *Śukranīti*, a compendium on polity composed by the Śvetāmbara abbot Jinadatta sūri of Vāyāda-gaccha who flourished during the early decades of 13th century. The work itself seems to have been completed by about 1209. As has been done by the author of the *Śukranīti*, Jinadatta sūri, too, devoted a few chapters on astrology, building rites, iconography, and architecture. The information embodied in the *Viveka-vilāsa* is relating to the plan and elevation of a classic Jaina temple. Though succinct, its significance is self-evident since it happens to be the work of a known date.

8. *Śrīdevyāvīrasambhavamāhātmya*

About 255 verses covering five chapters of this otherwise fragmentary work are available.²¹ It deals with the *jagatī*, the *mandovara*, the *prāsādaprastarā layanirṇaya*, and the temples of the Kamalodbhava and the Vijaya series. The text is cast in the form of a conversation between Īsvara and Devī. The age of the work is difficult to determine accurately because of the meagreness of details. But it could not be later than the 13th century as the style of writing suggests. Its temples of the Vijaya series are found quoted in *Śrījñānaratnakośa*. The temples of this series have been tabulated in a manuscript of 1629 from Sagwada in Mewar (copied therefrom by Prabhashankarbhai). The work is important in that it gives some data on the layout of the western Indian Jaina temple and the *jagatīs* for the Jaina temples.

Late Medieval

9. The *Vatthusāra payarāṇa*

A Jaina scholar by name Pheru of Karnal near Delhi wrote this *Vāstusāra-prakarāṇa* in Prakrit in A. D. 1326. The work comprises three chapters dealing respectively with the construction of dwelling houses (and the rites and astrological considerations), iconometry of Jaina images, and temple architecture. The text is too terse, furnishing only 68 verses á propos of temples. Its usefulness, like the *Viveka-vilāsa*, lies in its being a dated work providing some clues for fixing the age of the undated works. Although composed near Delhi, from the rules it enjoins and the terminology it uses, its theoretical position is very close to the tenets of the Maru-Gurjara school of the late Solāṅkī-Cāhamāna-Guhila periods. Its prescription regarding the introduction of *śimhathara* (lion-band) and *hamsathara* (gander-band) in the socle of the temple is, however, not upheld by western Indian texts, nor paralleled in any medieval temple in that vast region. This divergency notwithstanding, its allusion to the temples of the Kesarī series and the description of a characteristic *maṇḍovara* (wall face) certainly leads to the conclusion of its probable acquaintance with the works from Gujarat such as perhaps the *Aparājītaprcchā*.

10. The *Kṣīrāṇava*

Both Jaya and Aparājīta had been established as authorities to whom Viśvakarmā imparted his knowledge. In fact their names were repeatedly put to use by earlier writers with a consequent hackney that prompted the search for new figures to replace them. The writers now selected Devarṣi Nārada and brought him on the stage to converse with Viśvakarmā who, by his stature and antiquity as the Primordial Architect, had still maintained his supreme position as the divine exponent and transmitter of the art and science of architecture. The *Kṣīrāṇava* is also known as the *Nāradaprcchā*.

A number of manuscripts of this work are known, differing but little in contents from each other.²² None of these seems to cover more than 400 verses which are divided into 18 cognate chapters.²³ The very first chapter has been counted as 101, thus presupposing 100 chapters that preceded this. But this is rather intriguing in that none of these supposed preceding chapters is known from any source till now. The text sounds rather austere since it dispenses with all garnishments and in some cases even the descriptive details of architectural members. It strictly adheres to the metrography of elevational sections and the mouldings involved and then often does it with considerable precision and in detail as in the case of the *pīṭha* and the *maṇḍovara*. In view of these tendencies, it is very likely that the author shunned the preliminaries otherwise so much relished and unnecessarily elaborated by some of the earlier writers. This very fact is a pointer to the non-existence of preceding one hundred chapters: the text in fact consistently begins with

the *kūrmāsīlāmāna* (proportional measurements of the foundation stone of a temple) and next follows a regular cortège of other subjects. Among the topics that successively follow the first one are those pertaining to the base of the temple, the wall proper, the cella and the doorframe, the relative proportions of the image and the doorway, the locii of the eye-levels of gods, the *śikhara* and its details; next the temples of the Kesari series, the *maṇḍapas* and pillar types, and the proportional measurements of the wall-face of a temple with or without an ambulatory. Its exposition of the relative proportions of different structures and the architectural members and mouldings, is often, unlike some earlier works, more explicit, detailed, and clear.

Owing to references to the 14 classes of temples, the temples of Kesari series, the types of the *śukanāsa* (antefix on the fronton of the spire), the Rucakādi pillars and the Mervādi *maṇḍapas*, the text appears to be familiar with the *Aparājītaprcchā* or perhaps the *Vāstuśāstra* or both, although it does not borrow the phraseology of either. There are also slight indications that it was aware of the existence of the *Vāstuvīdyā*. On the other hand, some of its verses have been utilized in works whose date, from internal evidences, seems 15th century. The work, therefore, had been composed sometime after the 13th and before the 15th century. In its treatment of the *maṇḍovara* it betrays advances over the specifications of the earlier works. All the same, some of the peculiarities of décor noticeable on the 15th century temples are not paralleled in the text. This, together with the general tenor of expression found in the text, suggests rather a late 13th or early 14th century as the probable date of its composition though possibility of its being still later cannot be entirely ruled out.

Unlike earlier works, Viśvakarmā does not adopt a patronizing attitude towards the interlocutor in the *Kṣīrāṇava*. He addresses Nārada with considerable respect using such epithets as *mahāmuni*, *muniśvara*, and *ṛṣīraja*. This regard is reciprocated by Nārada, who, though pictured here as a recipient, has been reckoned as one of the leading ancient preceptors on architecture.²⁴ The *Nāradiya samhitā*, the *Nāradiya pañcarātra*, and the *Nāradiya śilpāsāstra*, southern works all, are ascribed to him.²⁵

11. The *Vrksārṇava*

One more work besides the *Kṣīrāṇava* where Nārada appears with Viśvakarmā is the *Vrksārṇava*. The later scribes were tricked by the suffix *arṇava* in the title as well as Nārada's participation and were thus led to confusing both the works. Some of the chapters of VK have been mixed up unwarily with those of KS, so much so that the opening verses in several manuscripts allude simultaneously to the *Kṣīrāṇava* as the exposition by Hari and the *Vrksārṇava* by Hara! This is obviously incorrect in as much as the exponent of both the works was Viśvakarmā; and what is more, the *Vrksārṇava* is decidedly posterior to the *Kṣīrāṇava* as a bulk of internal evidence does

not fail to suggest.

The text is available now in some rare, and incomplete, manuscripts.²⁶ Yet whatever is saved is at once an invaluable heritage and by the same token eminently significant to the study of the general western style of architecture in its late phase of its development. A later work though, VK is an ambitious product by virtue of its treatment of a number of topics not discussed by even the best among the earlier northern Indian *vāstu* authorities. This is in fact the *raison d'être* of this composition. The author consciously chose such topics as the forms of the *vedikā* (balustrated dado), the types of *prahāra* (base of the *śikhara*), 32 *devāṅganās* (celestial damsels), great storied *mandapas* such as Meghanāda, Harināda, Brahmanāda, Ravināda, Simhanāda, and Śivanāda, and *caturmukha* (four-faced) temples not touched by earlier writers. Partly this may indicate an advanced stage or a new turning in architectural development at that hour of the epoch. (That, incidentally, reveals the date of the composition of the work as will be established soon.) Nevertheless, its originality in treatment is quite apparent. This merit apart, the hyperzeal of the ambition has been carried, it may be admitted, too far, almost to the point of megalomania when the author coins such temple series as Mahādharādi, Napuṅsakādi, and Śaktisambharādi, where, in some cases thousands of *aṅḍakas* (turrets)²⁷ are involved in the make of the *śikhara*! The construction of such colossal, almost terrifying temples seems to transcend the practical limits of human efforts; at least such were never envisaged by the previous writers nor anywhere corresponded in actual examples. It unravels the transgression of the limit, the unpurposive drive, to which the fancy of the composer ran.

The date of the composition of the work may be conjectured with the aid of its inner statements. While the author attempted to explore all possible corners of originality, he had not been able to obviate influences of the authoritative works of the past so completely. His chapter on *āya* is just an amplification of the same subject treated in the *Vāstuvīdyā* and the *Aparājītaprcchā*. The original verses of VV and AP are resonant with pristine purity. The attempt at their synthesis, modification, and sandwiching of insertions rendered in VK reveals the intention of the author to bring within the fold as many objects and places for applying *āya* as he could conceive: the results, however, are amusing in that the author has gone to the length of including even a mosque in its perview under the name of Rahamāṇa prāsāda! Besides this, the description of the *caturmukha* temples for Jina and Śiva, *nāla-maṅḍapas* (halls above the stairways), *simhadvāras* (gates crowned by *kīrtimukha* masks), and *gavākṣa* (projected balcony) with *madalas* (struts) substituted for the *śikhara*'s *rathikā* (framed and pedimented divinity-bearing panel) referred to in the text conjure up the memories of the 15th century temples in Rajasthan and Gujarat. This is also true of the details of the *vedikā* and the *kaḥṣāsana* it visualizes: these features are noticeable only in the

15th century temples. The new idioms they reflect belong to the renaissance and not to the classical Solankī period. As usual with *vāstu* texts from western India, the Jaina deities have been accorded due place in the treatment in VK. The *parikara-lakṣaṇa* (characters of an image-frame) and iconometry of Jina image, the *talacchanda* (ground plan) of Jaina temples possessing 24, 52, 72, 84 and 108 *devakulikās* (chaplets) surrounding the main shrine, the directions for the construction of the symbolic *Aṣṭāpada*, *Nandīśvaradvīpa* and *Samavaśaraṇa* render it the most valuable work for the study of Jaina art and architecture as well. The strong partiality of the author for the *caturmukha* temples and his nostalgic return to it time and again is leading to a suspicion whether he himself was not connected with the construction of such a temple. The author seems a learned and versatile architect though the Sanskrit he employs is very ordinary. Echoes of the *Vrksārṇava* are very audibly heard in the far-famed *Caturmukha Dharaṇavihāra* (began A. D. 1440) sacred to *Ādinātha* at *Rāṇakpur*. Is it that illustrious designer and architect *Sūtradhāra Depāka* of that grand temple, who, overwhelmed by his own creation, decided to compose the *Vrksārṇava* wherein his obsession for the *caturmukha* temple is showing? The contents of the text at least betray *Rājasthānī* accents at places. And one of the types of *caturmukha* Jaina temples mentioned in the VK is 'Trailokyadīpaka', which was the type followed (according to a contemporary epigraph and literary sources) at *Rāṇakpur*!

An extraneous chapter covering some 116 verses from some unknown work is found mixed up with the available text of the *Vrksārṇava*. This intruder text deals with the temples, sacred to *Bhāskara* (Sun god) and the attendant shrines for the nine planets. It is framed in a form of dialogue between *Viśvakarmā* and *Rannā* (*Rājīdevī*), the consort of *Sūrya*. The Divine Master addresses the goddess as daughter (*putrī*, *tanayā*, *nandike*) during the conversation.

12. The *Vāstusāstrakārikā*

An incomplete work of uncertain date, it is available in the form of dialogues between *devas* (gods), *Brahmā*, and *Viśvakarmā*. Its known four chapters comprise such preliminary rites and other topics as the *bhūmi-parīkṣā* (testing of the soil or land), the *svapna-vidhi*, the *samayaśuddhi*, the *śilālakṣaṇa*, and the *grahakālanimāya* covering in all 405 verses.²⁸

13. The *Ratnatilaka*

This incompletely available work preserving about 125 verses starts with its third *paṭala* and advocates the rules for doorframes, temples, *śikharā* types, and the *āmalasāraka*. Its injunctions regarding the *lingalakṣaṇādvāra* have been quoted in *Śrījñānaratnaśoṣa*. It may have been composed in the 15th century.

14. The *Dipārṇava*

The age of relatively original works had ended with *Ratnatilaka*. The

subsequent writers were interested in compilations since the older works had long been established as authoritative works; and there was nothing much left to add when the architecture had been on an advanced march towards decadence. The *Dīpārnava*, also known in a number of manuscripts as the *Viśvakarmāvatāra*, the 14 chapters of which are known from several manuscripts in private and institutional collections, is verily a fragment of the earlier work, *Vāstuvidyā*, modified at places and mixed with excerpts from the *Vāstusāstra*, the *Aparājitaṅgachā*, the *Ksīrārnava*, and even the *Vrkṣārnava*²⁹. Its utility lies in the preservation of a part of the *Vāstuvidyā*, which can be collated with other sources for the restoration of the latter work. (The text of the published work also incorporates some recently composed passages.)

15. *Śrījñānaratnakośa*

This is another of the compilations which makes use of a number of older works, well concatenated in its earlier half but repetitive in subjects and confusing in contents in the latter part. The text does not run into regular chapters using though suitable pause-phrases to demarcate one topic from the other. At least two manuscripts of the work are known. The older one which is, on the strength of its characters, datable to 16th century, runs up to 1000 verses.³⁰ The younger one is a recent copy of a manuscript in turn copied in 1890 from an older manuscript dated 1549.³¹ The latter contains some 2752 verses. Stray portions of SRK are known from a number of short, or omnibus manuscripts. For such verses on rites as those concerning the *Vāstupuruṣa* and related matters, the *kalāsābhimantraṇa*, the *śāṅkulakṣaṇa*, and the *kīlakalakṣaṇa*, it has depended on the ancient Śaivāgamic work, the *Parameśvara mahātantra* of the southern canon. On the other hand, for the *sthapati-lakṣaṇa* and the *hasta-lakṣaṇa* which appear at the beginning of the text, it utilizes the *Samarāṅgaṇasūtradhāra*. The work in its last portion expresses its obligation to the *Vāstusāstra* of Viśvakarmā for such themes as the *jagatī*, the *pīṭha*, the *maṇḍovara*, the *garbhagrha*, the *dvāra*, the *rekhā*, and the 27 types of Puṣpakādi *maṇḍapas*.

The verses on the *āya*, the *marmavedha*, the *jagatī*, the *pīṭha*, the *katī* (*maṇḍovara* or wall proper), the *garbhamāna*, the *dhvajadanda*, and the *dvāralakṣaṇa* of the temples; also the articulation, proportions, and elevation of the *kolikā* (vestibular wall), the *maṇḍapa*, and the *karotaka* as well as the *saṁvaraṇā*-roof of the *maṇḍapa*, the Prāggrīva series of 33 types of *maṇḍapas*, the *liṅgalakṣaṇa* and the *liṅgāśrita devatās*; also the Sarvāṅgasundara prāsāda, the 12 forms of Sarasvatī, 24 forms of Umā, 12 forms of Āditya, the Dikpālas, the Grahas, and the Sapta-Mātrkās have all been borrowed, with some lapses and omissions, from the *Vāstuvidyā* specifically so acknowledged at a number of places. The differences between the *Vāstusāstra* and the *Vāstuvidyā* where the prescriptions on the same topics have been incorporated in *Śrījñānaratnakośa* are clearly conspicuous. The indebtedness

of the compilation to the *Aparājītaprcchā* is likewise in evidence, at places openly acknowledged. Its verses on the topics such as the *vāpī* (step-well), the *catuhkuṇḍa vārāṇasī* (four types of tanks), the *taṭāka* (reservoir), the *mahārājaveśma* (palace), *pañca toraṇa*, and 14 classes of temples are derived from the *Aparājītaprcchā*.

Aside from these major incorporations from the standard earlier *vāstu* works, a number of large and small passages as quotations from the less known works are also found in this compilation. *Śrīdevyāvīrasaṁbhava - mātmya* and the *Ratnatilaka* have been already mentioned in the foregoing pages. In addition, the *Rekhārnava* and the *Vāstuhṛdaya* (for *rekhās* of the *śikharas*), the *Ahivalaya* (for *śalyoḍdhāra vidhi*), the *Siddhārtha svargārohaṇa pātala* of Viśvakarmā (for Gokulādi prāsādas to be constructed as memorials after the dead), the *Pramāṇa-kośa*, the *Hiṇḍolā pātala* of Malaya (for *ḍolācakra*) and the *Pratiṣṭhāsāra* of Āditya (for *pāśāna-parīkṣā*), and finally the *Īśānaśivagurudevapaddhati*, a wellknown South Indian work, has been utilized for the forms of Viṣṇu. There are also quotations from works whose titles are unknown. As instances, the *yantra-vāhana lakṣaṇa* expounded in a dialogue form between Bhairava and Devī and the *rathādhāra* presented as a conversation between Brahmā and Viṣṇu may be noted. The text begins to sprawl aimlessly in the latter half of the book; it almost becomes an agglomerate just as the grammatical errors are on the increase. All the same, it is very informative in its overall contents. Several older works, now lost or partially available, find their place in this collection. Some of the rarer kind of information furnished by *Śrījñānaratnakośa* pertains to the formal details of such important decorative motifs as the *vyāla* and the *makara*.

It is not quite easy to fix the precise date of this compilation. Most of the works quoted in its corpus are the wellknown works of the medieval period and several others the dates of which are not known; it is, therefore, very likely to be post-Solankī. Its very title sounds late. We are reminded of such work as the *Nrttaratnakośa* and the *Pāthyaratnakośa*, the composition of both of which is ascribed to Mahārāṇā Kumbhakarna of Chitor. Of course, there is no indication in *Śrījñānaratnakośa* that could associate it with that great patron of art and letters, who flourished in the latter half of 15th century, nor works on *vāstu* definitely known of that century could be traced within the fabric of this compilation. But the parallelism in denomination would at least point to a prevailing fashion of the age. Its upper limit is fixed by the date of one of the two manuscripts and the characters of the other one, which would thus be not later than the 16th century. The age of *Śrījñānaratnakośa* could, therefore, be placed sometime in the 15th century or slightly earlier.

16-24. Works of Sūtradhāra Maṇḍana

The latter half of 15th century is symptomatic of a breakthrough in one

aspect; the authors and compilers of the *vāstu* texts cast off the disguise of the dialogue form of writing and openly came forward with the admission of their own authorship as was in fact done in that period in southern India as exemplified by the *Tantrasamuccaya* of Nārāyaṇa (A. D. 1426). This bravado is, however, not matched by a creative originality, for most of the writers sought their inspiration from the fountainhead of the earlier authoritative works. The architectural style both in Rajasthan and Gujarat had passed the peak of perfection four centuries before and had by now entered the phase of relative senility. What purpose could these fresh compilations have served at this stage is a moot point. Whether apprehensive of the probable extinction of the tradition and hence the frantic drive by several authors to rescue it by fresh codifications, or expressive naturally of the mood of a renaissance period when the style, if it could not be revitalized, saw its further degeneration checked for a while, needs some inquiry. A peep into the historical setting of the time and a visit to the monumental remains of the period furnish explanation of the whole problem.

The end of the 13th century marked the advent of Muslims at first as invaders and next as rulers in Gujarat. A few Rājaputa centres spared at the time eventually became powerful till Sultan Mahammad II of Ahmedabad put an end to the Cūḍāsamā rule at Junagarh in 1469 and subjugated the Rāvalas of Champaner in 1484. The third centre, Idar, too was hard pressed by Mahammad's son Muzaffar Shah II between 1511-15, and although it managed to survive the adversities with difficulties, suffered heavily during the periods of sieges and dethronements of princes. It was precisely before these fatal times that these centres teemed with brisk architectural activities. The Samarasimha's temple (1438), the Melaka vasahī (c. 1438), the Pūrnasimha vastī (c. 1438) and the so-called temple of Samprati Rājā (1453) on Mt. Girnār, next the seven Jaina temples on Pavagarh Hill near Champaner, the great temple of Gadādhara at Samalaji, Saraneśvara temple near Ābhāpar together with the Jaina temples at Bhilodā, Raigadh, Pratāpgadh, and Harnā Valley at Polo and Derol (to mention only the most notable) in Idar area are the erections of this general period in Gujarat. The neighbouring contemporaneous Rajasthan enjoyed even more stable peace and consequent cultural achievements. Among the noteworthy monuments of this age are the Kirtistambha (1449), the *śikhara* and the *sarivaraṇā* of the late Maurya temple of Viṣṇu (c. early 8th cent.) rechristened as Kumbhasvāmī (1449), and the so-called Mīrābāi's temple, the Mānastambha (1485) beside the Digambara Jaina temple - all situated within the fort with Rānā pratolī (1459) at Chitor-, the Kumbhasvāmī temple at Achalgadh on Mt. Abu, the fort of Kumbhalagadh with the temple of Kumbhasvāmī (1460), and Kumbhmaṇḍapa at Eklingī are edifices whose *kārāpaka* or builder is Mahārāṇā Kumbhā himself. Besides, the temple of Somnātha at Dungarpur, the Nalinīgulmavimāna (1440) and the temples of Pārsvanātha, Neminātha, and Sūrya at Rānakpur, the *caturmukha*

temple of Pārśvanātha (1459) on Mt. Ābu, the Jaina temple near Mirpur or Hamirgaḥ, the Ādinātha temple at Sirohi, the Pārśvanātha temple at Varkānā, the Ādinātha and the Pārśvanātha temples at Delvādā near Ekalingjī, and the Jaina temple at Kelvādā are other notable temples of this period in Rajasthan. In the distant Jesalmer, a number of highly embellished Jaina temples were built during this age. The temple of Cintāmaṇi Pārśvanātha (1417) with its fine *torana* in front, the temple of Sambhavanātha (1442), the temple of Rṣabha (1453) and the temple of Sāntinātha (1480) there precisely fit in the times invoked in this context. Despite variations in regional inflexions, temples in all these territories betray certain fundamental oneness in expression along with the presence of a few typical, diagnostic features such as the *kūtacchādyā* (hood) supported by *madalas*, complex *prahāra*, and the *gavākṣas* with *madalas* in lieu of *rathikās* in the *śikhara* never known before this age in either Gujarat or Rajasthan. The replacement of the *bhūmī-āmalakas* or *karnāṇdakas* in the *veṇukośa* (segmented, curved corners) of the *śikhara* by a sort of a *ghaṭapallava* and at times by *śikharikā* motif which was to find greater favour in subsequent centuries, is also ubiquitous in this age at a number of centres. This then was a brief but a brilliant period of glory for the late medieval style of western Indian architecture. These favourable circumstances gave a philip to the composition, among other literary works, of those on *vāstu* art as well. Happily, at the spur of the moment, the munificent and powerful royal patron was found in Mahārānā Kumbhā of Chitor. At his court flourished several men of letters at the behest of which stood scholarly Maṇḍana, the Architect Royale who composed a number of works on iconography and architecture. Whether Maṇḍana belonged to Gujarat and was invited by Mahārānā Kumbhā at his court to compose the *vāstusāstras* as one tradition and a late copperplate inscription purport to say is true or not, cannot be ascertained conclusively. On the other hand, on the strength of several colophons of Maṇḍana's works, R. C. Agrawal favours the view that Maṇḍana and his father belonged to Mewar proper though the possibility of their forefathers having hailed from Gujarat cannot be altogether discounted.³² Be that it may, Maṇḍana's works evidently show close acquaintance with the *vāstu* works from Gujarat.

At least eight works of Maṇḍana are known. These are by name the *Prāsādamaṇḍana*, the *Vāstumāṇḍana*, the *Vāsturājavallabhamāṇḍana*, the *Vāstusāra*, the *Vāstusāstra*, the *Rūpamaṇḍana*, the *Rūpāvatāra*³³ and the *Devatāmūrtiprakaraṇa*. The exact date of none of these works is so far known; but a relative chronological position of a few can be ascertained by a comparative study. The *Vāsturājavallabha*, for instance, seems a recast, and an abridged one, of the *Vāstumāṇḍana*; the *Vāstusāra* is just a summary of either the *Vāsturājavallabha* or the *Vāstumāṇḍana*.

The *Vāstumāṇḍana* contains 865 verses divided into eight cognate chapters. Besides astrological considerations, subjects on the construction of mansions,

palaces, tanks, forts etc. have been treated. The earlier works such as *Matsyapurāna*, the *Mayamata*, the *Jayapṛcchā*, the *Vivekavilāsa*, and the *Aparājitapṛcchā* had been the basis for some of its material. The sister text, the *Vāsturājavallabha*, consists of 14 chapters covering about 475 verses.³⁴ A variety of meters have, however, been used in the versification in this booklet. The subjects of discussion are identical. The *Vāstuśāstra* pays more attention to treating the rites. The *Prāsādamaṇḍana* has freely borrowed material from the *Aparājitapṛcchā*. The *Rūpamaṇḍana* is a text on iconometry and iconography of Brahmanical and Jaina deities. It covers six chapters in 350 verses. The *Rūpāvatāra* which closely resembles the *Rūpamaṇḍana*, comprises 500 verses and may be the earlier of the two. The *Devatāmūrtiprakaraṇa* which in certain cases is more explicit than RV and RM, contains 500 verses cast into eight chapters. The work for the most part draws from the *Aparājitapṛcchā* and another source not so far detected. Forms of Brahmā, Brahmāyatana and Brahmā's attendants, Sūrya's *āyatana* and his *pratihāras*, also Vaikuṅṭha, Ananta, and Trailokyamohana forms of Viṣṇu, Viṣṇu's *āyatana* and attendants, Aṣṭa-Dikpālas, 11 forms of Rudra, composite image as of Ardhanārīśvara, Kṛṣṇa-Śaṅkara, and Hari-Hara-Pitāmaha, and besides them Umā-Maheśvara, also some of the liṅga types and their characteristics, 12 forms of Gaurī, Gaurī's *dvārapālikās*, Gaṇeśāyatana and *pratihāras* of Gaṇeśa, Pañca-Līlayādevīs and Navadurgā, 24 Tīrthaṅkaras, their colour complexions, banners, Yakṣas and Yakṣīs, are clearly derived from the *Aparājitapṛcchā*. On the other hand, slight influences of the *Vāstuvīdyā* and the *Mayamata* are also detectable.³⁵

26. The *Vāstumañjarī/Prāsādamañjarī*

Sūtradhāra Nātha or Nāthu, younger brother of Maṇḍana, composed this relatively less known work consisting of 1100 verses divided into three sections (*stabakas*) The first one deals, like the *Vāsturājavallabha*, with *vāstu* rites and the civic as well as military architecture. The second part sometimes available as a detached work, popularly called the *Prāsādamañjarī*, purports to deal with temple architecture as its denomination suggests and reminds the better known *Prāsādamaṇḍana*. The third part of VM, like the *Rūpamaṇḍana*, and the *Rūpāvatāra*, dwells on iconography. Nātha mentions Mahārāṇa Rājamalla as the contemporary ruler in Mevād. Hence his work seems to fall in the last quarter of 15th century.

27-29. Works of Govinda

At least three works of Sūtradhāra Govinda, son of Maṇḍana, are known to be in existence in manuscript form in several collections.³⁶ His *Kalānidhī* comprising 251 verses divided into eight chapters (*aṣṭa prakāśas*) treats the elevational aspects of the *śikhara*. His *Dvāradīpikā* is still briefer and deals with the metrical and other features of the doorframe. The third work, the *Vāstoddhāradhorāṇī*, discusses the ways, means, and purport of renovating

temples, images, and palaces. In this work he has quoted Nārada, Brahmā, Manu, Sārvadeva, Jaya, Maya, and Aparājita. The work embodies some 305 verses.

The earlier half of the 16th century is a dark age; but influential ministers at the Court of the Sultans of Gujarat could persuade the rulers in permitting temple building. Karmāśā's renovation of the great temple of Adinātha (1531) on Śatruñjaya Hills is one of such few wellknown examples. But it was from the last decades of that century to about the middle of the 17th century, a second phase of renaissance, though of less lustre, commenced. This was in the main promoted by the policy of tolerance adopted by the Mughal Emperor Akbar and to some extent by his son and successor Jahangir. The influential position held by the great Jaina pontiff Jagadguru Śrī Hīravijaya sūri of Tapā-gaccha and Jinacandra sūri of Kharatara-gaccha at the Mughal court actuated the quick resumption of temple building activities in Gujarat and in Rajasthan. Vijaysena sūri (the disciple of Hīravijaya sūri), and Vijayadeva sūri, Upādhyāya Kalyāṇavijaya, and Kalyāṇasāgara sūri who followed Vijayasena sūri, embarked on a long programme of preaching that led to some extensive projects of reconsecration and renovation of older fanes, the rehabilitation of Jaina centres, and construction of new Jaina temples.

Among the notable new temples that were built during this phase were the Caturmukha temple (1578) at Sirohi, Indravihāra (1588) at Vairāt, temple of Cintāmaṇi Pārśvanātha (1588) and Tejapāla Sonī's temple (1590) at Khambhāt, the Caturmukha temple of Gandhāriya (1585), the Jaina temple (1598) at Kavi, the temple of Candraprabha (1606), and the Caturdvāra vihāra of Manotamalla (1619), both again on Śatruñjaya, the Rājavihāra (1602) at Bhuj, the Pārśvanātha temple (1606) at Bhinnamāl, the temple of Candraprabha (1610) at Prabhāsa, the Adinātha temple (1618) at Nagaur, the Anandajī Abji's temple (1633), the Neṇaśiśā's temple, and the temple of Śāntinātha (1616-22) by Vardhamāna-Padmasimha, and the Caturmukha Sambhavanātha temple (1640) of Raiśiśā at Jamnagar, the Jaina temple (1628) by Sheth Śāntidāsa at Ahmedabad, and finally the temple of Śāntinātha (1635) at Porbandar. Among the brahmanical temples of this period, the more notable are the Jagadīśa temple (1652) at Udaipur and the temple of Jagatśiromani at Amber near Jaipur (16th cent.), both in Rajasthan.

The fervent architectural activities of the period seem to be matched by a few compositions of *vāstu* texts. Their merits are as worthy as the qualities of a decaying style of architecture could be. In all probability, the undernoted works form a group cognately attributable to this final phase.

30. The *Vāsturāja*

The work has been composed by Sūtradhāra Rājasimha whose exact date is not known. One of the two known manuscripts of VR, however, bears

the date s. 1685 (A.D. 1629); Rājasimha should have flourished sometime before that date. The latter manuscript contains 509 verses and runs up to ten chapters.³⁷ The second manuscript comprises 13 chapters covering 600 verses. The work deals with *vāstu* rites, elevation of a temple, and temple types. Its main source of extraction is the *Aparājitapṛcchā*; however, it also depends on the *Vāstuvīdyā* and the *Kṣīrārṇava* as well. The *Vāsturāja* is sometimes mentioned in the later notes of the śilpīns as *iti sūtradhāre*.

31. The *Vāsturāja Vāstuśāstra*

Only second and third chapters of this extensive compilation are known.³⁸ Its compiler's name is, however, uncertain. The available portion comprises as many as 1500 verses; it deals with *vāstu* rites, astronomical-astrological considerations, and civic and domestic architecture. It has quoted a number of previous authorities such as Manu, Vaśiṣṭha, Garga, Viśvakarmā, Jaya, Maya, Aparājita, the *Matsyapurāṇa*, the *Viṣṇudharmottara*, the *Mārkaṇḍeyapurāṇa*, the *Varāḥapurāṇa-saṁhitā*, the *Bṛhatsaṁhitā*, the *Kīranatantra*, the *Samarāṅganāsūtradhāra*, the *Vāstuvīdyā*, the *Lakṣaṇasamuccaya*, the *Vāstumāṇḍana*, and the *Vāsturātṅakara*. Since *Vāstumāṇḍana* has been quoted in this work, the compilation must be post-Māṇḍana. On the other hand, an omnibus manuscript of 1629 quotes it. Hence the compilation is bracketed between these limits.

32. The *Vāstukambāsūtra*

Sukhānanda is the author of this work which covers some 600 verses in seven chapters (*bhūmikās*);³⁹ it resembles the *Vāsturājavallabha* in treatment and choice of subjects. It quotes the *Matsyapurāṇa*, the *Līlāvāṭī*, and Ācārya Śrīdhara. Stylistically, it may be of late 15th or early 16th century.

33. The *Prāsādatilaka*

Sūtradhāra Virapāla was the author of this small work, the four chapters of which covering 93 verses are available.⁴⁰ It discusses matters concerning temple, images, and astrology. Like the *Vāsturājavallabha*, in lieu of normal Anuṣṭubha meter, it uses Sārdūlavikṛīḍita. The work seems post-Māṇḍana.

34. The *Vāstutilaka*

The available portion of this work by one Keśava consists of 11 chapters (*paricchedas*) comprising 400 verses. It deals with *vāstu* rites and domestic architecture.

35. The *Vāstukautuka*

Guṇeśa is the author of this work which consists of six chapters covering 414 verses. It treats astrology and domestic architecture. It quotes Garga and Māṇḍana.

36. The *Śilpadīpaka*

This work, ascribed to Śilpī Gaṅgādhara treats astronomical-astrological

aspects of domestic architecture.⁴¹ It comprises six chapters. It has depended on the *Samarāṅgaṇasūtradhāra*, the *Aparājītaprocchā*, and the *Vāsturājavalabha*.

This survey points out to a fairly satisfactory position with regard to the availability of the Sanskrit works on the medieval and late medieval architecture of Gujarat and Rajasthan. Between the older northern works such as the *Matsyapurāna* (older parts 5th cent.), the *Brhatsamhitā* (mid 6th cent.) the *Visnudharmottara* (7th cent.), the *Hayasīrsa-pañcarātra* (8th cent.), and such other early works known through quotations as the *Kāśyapasamhitā*, the *Gārgīsamhitā* and the *Kiraṇatantra* on one hand and the works on medieval architecture on the other, there is a lacuna of about three centuries which is yet to be filled in. Bhaṭṭa Utpala (9th cent.) who commented on the *Brhatsamhitā*, quotes a self-composed work entitled the *Vāstuvidyā*. This work possibly pertained to *vāstu* rites and astronomical-astrological matters, and not to the detailed structural rules for buildings. The term *vāstu* embraced a wider connotation in the medieval period only. The chapter "Vāstu lakṣaṇa" in the *Brhatsamhitā*, for instance, restricts its concern to ritual and allied considerations. Hence Utpala's work, even if it should some day see daylight, is not likely to add much to the knowledge on the constructional and structural aspects of architecture. In one case, however, a sort of continuity may be perceived. The *Hayasīrsa-pañcarātra* and the *Agnipurāna*, composed as they were in eastern India, have left a descendent in the *Lakṣaṇasamuccaya* of Vairocana, a work perhaps of the 11th or 12th century and probably from the same general provenance. This is the impression gathered from the perusal of the work. In point of fact, the *Hayasīrsa-pañcarātra* itself shows a little advance over earlier works in the syntax and fund of terms and the proportional measurements of the different parts of temples. The *Lakṣaṇasamuccaya* shows a distinct nexus with the latter text in terminology and mannerism of expression. It has a look, archaistic and atavistic, though much of its contents from its known portion are emblematic of medieval architecture of a region apparently bordering between Orissa and Bengal.

From the latter half of the eighth century, a number of mutually allied, cognate, well defined, and forceful architectural traditions began to prevail in definite centres and sectors of Rajasthan and northern Gujarat, and thus in western India. These eventually blossomed into various superb, ornate schools of the medieval period in these provinces. The oldest *vāstu* works known from these territories embody the knowledge of a style which was then crossing its high watermark. They are elaborate compendia of a fully mature style, the works whose injunctions could be applied to the temples erected between eighth and tenth centuries are next to none. During this intervening period were created some of the finest masterpieces of temple architecture in north India. Having regard to the fact, it is difficult to assume that this interval could have been sterile in the production of corresponding written records on *vāstu*. Some day, perhaps, the gap will be bridged, thanks to chance

discoveries of such works from the hitherto untrodden corners. And then what seems today a sharp contrast between the earlier and the medieval works, may disappear, and, instead, a gradual evolution in the textual tradition, also in the structural features and rules of proportions together with terminology may be perceived as a spasmodic response to the evolution in the field of architecture. The writings of the *Vāstuśāstrakāras* of the 11th century then might not have been actuated by the need of replacing the codes of the Gupta and post-Gupta masters, but a logical carry over, a revision and an amplification of the knowledge gained and preserved possibly in the writings of the tenth century. Verily, the *Samarāṅganasūtradhāra*, and the *Lakṣaṇasamuccaya* as well, reveal, behind their apparent screen of homogeneous style, the presence of a few hidden nebulae whose archaism has been deliberately masked, even transformed to harmonize with the stage of evolution triumphant in the 11th century. These are interesting, indeed very interesting problems to be sure, but out of the scope of the present paper whose intention is to present a brief (and rapid) survey of the known material.⁴²

Notes and References

1. *Garga—or Gārgi-saṁhita* ?
2. Kaśyapa as quoted by Bhaṭṭa Utpala in his commentary on the *Brhatsaṁhita*. This was different from, and earlier than, the Vaikhānasa work, the *Kāśyapasamhitā* (c. 10th cent. A. D.), and the *Kāśyapa-śilpaśāstra* (c. 13th cent.) of southern India. Another lost work is the *Prāsādalakṣaṇa* ascribed to Nagnajita.
3. The later work, the *Viśvakarmāprakāśa*, seems to have been based on the original work ascribed to Parāśara.
4. Manu converses with Matsya in the *Matsyapurāna*.
5. The *Viṣṇudharmottara* (Tṛtīya khaṇḍa).
6. One manuscript is preserved in the collection of the Oriental Institute, Baroda. Some portions of the work had been copied by Shri Prabhashankarbai from two different mss. of the 17th century. The author is deeply grateful to late Drs. B. J. Sandesara and U. P. Shah for permitting examination of the valuable collection of the Oriental Institute.
7. The *Jayapr̥cchā* was to be edited by Shri Prabhashankarbai and the present author. Shri Prabhashankarbai, unfortunately, passed away before we could prepare the final press-manuscript of this and those of the several other works we were jointly editing.
8. D. N. Shukla has published these studies in his *Vāstuśāstra*, Vol. I, *Hindu Science of Architecture*, Lucknow (1961 ?).
9. Shri Hemachandracharya Jnanabhandara at Patan, the Oriental Institute, Baroda,

the L. D. Institute of Indology, Ahmedabad, and the Asiatic Society of Bombay are foremost among the institutions that possess such manuscripts. Asiatic Society of Bengal, Calcutta, is also in possession of the mss. of the *vāstu* works from western India. Among the hereditary architects, excellent collections were with Shri Prabhaskar O. Sompura (the editor of the *Dīpārṇava* and the *Prāsādamañjarī*), late Shri Narmadashankar Sompura (The compiler of the *Śīparatnākara*), Shri Amritlal Trivedi (Sompura), Shri Mansukhlal Sompura, Champalalji Sompura of Sādri, Shri Bhanvarlalji of Udaipur, and a few other architects.

10. The *Aparājītapṛcchā* seems to have made condensations from this work.
11. An effort had been made by Shri Prabhaskarbhai and the present writer to re-assemble this valuable text as far as possible.
12. The sequence of mouldings in both the texts for the *pīṭha* is the same. As for the *dhvajanda*, the verse 24 in chapter CIL of AP closely resembles a corresponding verse in VV.
13. The detailed comparison of the two texts has been reserved for another occasion.
14. The term *kaṭi* occurs in older texts. AP and a number of other works from western India use the term *maṇḍovara* instead.
15. The now wellknown 100 verses beginning with *arūpaṃ rūpamākāram...* describing the Jina image originally belonged to the *Vāstuvidyā*.
16. This work must not be confounded with the work of the same title from south India.
17. M. P. Vora and M. A. Dhaky, "The Date of *Aparājītapṛcchā*," *Journal of the Oriental Institute*, Vol. IX, No. 4, Baroda, 1960.
18. M. A. Dhaky, "The influence of *Samarāṅgaṇasūtradhārā* on *Aparājītapṛcchā*," *Journal of the Oriental Institute*, Baroda, Vol. X, No. 3.
19. As evidenced by a verse in the chapter on flag staff. Besides, the description of the Rucakādi-prāsādas as well as the Tilakasāgarādi-prāsādas in AP seems just the condensation, with a few alternations, of the same given in VV.
20. A manuscript of the work existed in the collection of Shri Prabhaskarbhai.
21. It is not certain whether the *Aparājītapṛcchā* and the *Aparājītaprabhā* are not identical. Possibly, this one is a lost chapter of the *Aparājītapṛcchā*. (The *Aparājītaprabhā* in the collection of the Asiatic society of Bengal seems to contain material from the *Aparājītapṛcchā*.)
22. I noticed these in the collection of Oriental Institute, Baroda, Shri Prabhaskarbhai, and a few other traditional architects.
23. It was examined by the author over three decades ago. The text since then has been published by Shri Prabhaskarbhai.
24. According to the list of the *Matsyapurāna*; the *Agnipurāna* refers to the *Nāradya-tantra*.
25. A manuscript of the *Nāradyasamhitā* exists in the collection of Oriental Institute, Baroda.

26. Late Shri Prabhashankarbhai had plans to publish this valuable work.
27. The *aṅḍakas* are of two types: one in the form of miniature Latina, the other is Anekāṅḍaka-Nāgara, called *karma* in the medieval texts.
28. The manuscripts are preserved in the collection of Oriental Institute, Baroda.
29. The text has been recently edited and published by Late Shri Prabhashankarbhai.
30. This I had noticed in the collection of Shri Prabhashankarbhai.
31. This is in the collection of Oriental Institute, Baroda.
32. R. C. Agrawal, "Mevāḍa ke kuśala sūtradhāra evaṁ śilpi," (Hindi) *Sammelana-patrikā, Kalā aṅka*.
33. Except perhaps three, all the rest are published.
34. Published by various agencies.
35. Haridas Mitra, in his introduction to the *Devatāmūrtiprakaraṇa*, writes: "For compiling his *DMP Sūtradhāra Maṅḍana* seems either to have chiefly utilized the South Indian texts, or to have actually based his work on them." This observation is untenable; the text in the main depends on AP.
36. These works have not been published as far as known.
37. This work I had noticed in the collection of Shri Prabhashankarbhai.
38. Shri Prabhashankarbhai was in possession of a recent copy of the only known ms. of this work.
39. The work is also known as the *Sukhānanda-vāstu*.
40. This, too, was noticed in the collection of Shri Prabhashankarbhai.
41. Published long back by M/s Mahadev Ramchandra Jaguste, Ahmedabad.
42. This short essay had been written some 28 years ago in the form of a prologue to my long "Introduction" to the *Prāsādamañjarī* edited by late Shri Prabhashankarbhai. As the turn of events decreed, it could not be completed and incorporated in the published text of the *Prāsādamañjarī*. It is, therefore, published here, as it then was, for the first time with a few minor revisions. I am deeply indebted to late Shri Prabhashankarbhai for permitting me to examine his valuable collection of the manuscripts and transcripts of the *vāstu* works. With profound sadness, I have prefixed his name with the word 'late' as also before the names of Dr. B. J. Sandesara and Dr. U. P. Shah both of whom had been my well-wishers and supporters.